

Dynamic Properties and Construction of Piecewise Smooth Periodic Solutions of Integro-Differential Equations

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A spatially distributed integro-differential equation with periodic boundary conditions is considered. It is assumed that the solution has zero mean over the spatial variable. The boundary value problem under consideration has a family of piecewise constant on the spatial variable solutions with one discontinuity point. The stability conditions for such solutions are defined. The existence of the piecewise constant solutions having more than one point of discontinuity is shown. During the numerical experiment, an algorithm based on the method of expansions in Fourier series has been used. With its help, it was expedient to calculate solutions to a boundary value problem that satisfies the condition of zero mean. We numerically study the behavior of the solutions to the boundary value problem for $\beta \neq 1$ outside the domain of an α -stable one-parameter family of piecewise constant solutions. The presence of α -stable piecewise constant solutions with more than one discontinuity point is shown. A numerical analysis of the dynamics of the boundary value problem has been carried out.

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1. Introduction

Consider the spatially distributed integro-differential equation

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} = \xi - \beta(\xi^2 - M(\xi^2)) - (1 - \beta)(\xi^3 - M(\xi^3)), \quad (1.1)$$

where $\beta \in [0, 1]$, $\xi = \xi(t, x)$ at each $t \geq 0$ is a piecewise smooth function on the spatial variable x

$$M(\xi) = \int_0^1 \xi(t, x) dx.$$

Equation (1.1) is considered with a periodic boundary condition

$$\xi(t, x + 1) = \xi(t, x) \quad (1.2)$$

and the additional condition of zero on the spatial variable mean

$$M(\xi) = 0. \quad (1.3)$$

Problems of this type arise in the construction of quasi-normal forms for nonlinear equations describing the dynamics of a wide class of systems of functional-differential equations with infinite-dimensional degeneration.

In the case of finite-dimensional degenerations, the problem of the stability of the zero solution uses the standard method of normal forms. This method is well described in classical books [1–4] for the finite-dimensional phase space and in books [5, 6] for the infinite-dimensional case. If in the problem of the stability of the zero solution the degeneracy is infinite-dimensional, then to construct the quasinormal form one can formally use the same algorithms as before, but the proof of the correspondence theorems is a separate complex problem.

Let us briefly describe the models in the

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analysis of which the boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3) appears. First of all, we note the works in which the dynamics of equations and systems of equations with a large delay coefficient from optoelectronics are investigated [7–10]. When studying the local dynamics of these models, the characteristic quasi-polynomial of the system linearized on its equilibrium state has infinitely many roots, which tend to the imaginary axis when the lag factor increases. Thus, the critical case of infinite dimensionality in the equilibrium state stability problem is realized. In [7], an asymptotic algorithm for constructing a first approximation system for the solutions of such models was developed. This algorithm is based on the transition to partial derivative equations. As it turns out, the location of the roots of the characteristic quasi-polynomial determines the boundary conditions for the constructed partial derivative equations as well. Such boundary conditions are both periodic and antiperiodic boundary conditions as well as periodic and antiperiodic boundary conditions with the additional condition that the mean value of the partial derivative equation solutions is zero. The nonlocal dynamics of the boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3) defines the behavior of solutions of the initial dynamical system with initial conditions from some sufficiently small neighborhood of the equilibrium state.

Singularly perturbed problems of parabolic type [11, 12] are also a source of such type of boundary conditions. In them the equation of the first approximation contains an arbitrary parameter as a multiplier at the high spatial derivative. Therefore there is a problem of investigation including equations without space derivatives, but with boundary conditions including the condition of equality to zero of mean value of solutions and with nonlinear terms in equation of the first approximation, which are obtained by averaging on spatial variable.

Also note that the equations with complex variables, similar to the problem (1.1)-(1.2) of the form, arise in the study of fully coupled oscillator systems (see [13–15]), and the condition (1.3) of zero mean may be needed in addition to them.

If the number of interacting oscillators tends to infinity, we obtain a continuous model of the same type as the boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3).

This paper investigates the dynamics of solutions of the boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3) at different values of the parameter β . The existence of a family of piecewise constant solutions of the boundary value problem is proved. The question about the so-called α -stability of these solutions is considered. To illustrate the results of the analytical study of problem (1.1)-(1.3), its solutions are constructed by numerical methods.

2. Existence of piecewise constant solutions with one discontinuity point

In this section of the paper we turn to the problem of existence of piecewise constant solutions of the boundary value problem (1.1)–(1.3). In this connection we note that to find such solutions it is sufficient to fulfill the conditions (1.1)–(1.2). The property (1.3) is obtained by integrating from 0 to 1 over the spatial variable of the (1.1) equation, taking into account the (1.2) condition and the equality of the time derivative to zero.

Consider the case $\beta = 1$ where equation (1.1) contains only quadratic nonlinearity. Let us show that if this condition is satisfied, there exists a one-parameter family of piecewise constant solutions.

Let us represent the desired function in the form

$$\xi(t, x) = \begin{cases} a, & 0 \leq x < \alpha, \\ b, & \alpha \leq x < 1, \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

where a, b, α – some nonzero constants, with $a \neq b$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. For the function (2.1) we assume that the condition (1.2) of periodicity on the spatial variable is satisfied.

Let us substitute (2.1) into (1.1), then on the interval $0 \leq x < \alpha$ we get equality

$$a - (a^2 - (\alpha a^2 + (1 - \alpha)b^2)) = 0,$$

and on the interval $\alpha \leq x < 1$ we have

$$b - (b^2 - (\alpha a^2 + (1 - \alpha)b^2)) = 0.$$

Subtracting equalities from each other, we obtain $(a - b)(1 - a - b) = 0$. Considering that $a \neq b$, we have $a + b = 1$. If we now add the first of the equations multiplied by α with the second one multiplied by $1 - \alpha$, we obtain the equality $\alpha a + b(1 - \alpha) = 0$, which represents the condition (1.3) of the zero mean for the solution (2.1). Thus, with α fixed, one can determine the numbers a and b in formula (2.1)

$$a = \frac{1 - \alpha}{1 - 2\alpha}, \quad b = \frac{\alpha}{1 - 2\alpha}.$$

Note that at $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$ there is no function of the form (2.1).

The following statement is true.

Lemma 2.1. *The boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3) at $\beta = 1$ has a family of parameter-dependent $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, $\alpha \neq \frac{1}{2}$ piecewise constant solutions on the spatial variable x of the form*

$$\xi(t, x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1-\alpha}{1-2\alpha}, & 0 \leq x < \alpha, \\ -\frac{\alpha}{1-2\alpha}, & \alpha \leq x < 1. \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

Cases $\beta = 0$ and $\beta \in (0, 1)$ are similarly considered. In this connection we can formulate the following two statements.

Lemma 2.2. *The boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3) at $\beta = 0$ has two families of parameter-dependent $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ piecewise constant on the spatial variable x solutions of the form*

$$\xi(t, x) = \begin{cases} \pm \frac{1-\alpha}{\sqrt{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2}}, & 0 \leq x < \alpha, \\ \mp \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2}}, & \alpha \leq x < 1. \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

Lemma 2.3. *The boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3) at $\beta \neq 0$ and $\beta \neq 1$ has two families of piecewise constant on the spatial variable x solutions of the form*

$$\xi(t, x) = \begin{cases} a(\alpha), & 0 \leq x < \alpha, \\ b(\alpha), & \alpha \leq x < 1, \end{cases} \quad (2.4)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a(\alpha) &= \frac{-\beta(1-\alpha)(1-2\alpha) \pm (1-\alpha)D}{2(1-\beta)(1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2)}, \\ b(\alpha) &= \frac{\alpha\beta(1-2\alpha) \mp \alpha D}{2(1-\beta)(1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2)}, \\ D &= \sqrt{\beta^2(1-2\alpha)^2 + 4(1-\beta)(1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2)}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

The results of this part of the paper can be generalized if the intervals of constancy of the function (2.1) be replaced by an arbitrary measurable subset of the segment $[0, 1]$. Obviously, the results of lemmas 2.1, 2.2, and 2.3 do not depend on the kind of set on which the function takes values a and b , but depend only on the measure of these sets. If we put

$$\xi(t, x) = \begin{cases} a, & x \in E, \\ b, & x \in [0, 1] \setminus E, \end{cases} \quad (2.6)$$

where $E \subset [0, 1]$, $\text{mes } E = \alpha$, then the formulations of lemmas 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 will remain in the same form. At the same time, the representation in the form (2.1) is more illustrative; besides, for solutions of this kind one can introduce the α -stability property and investigate the constructed solutions for the presence or absence of this property.

3. α -stability of piecewise constant solutions

Let us define the notion of α -stable piecewise constant solution.

Let $\alpha_0 = 0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \dots < \alpha_{k+1} = 1$ and

$$\xi_*(x) = \{\rho_j, \text{ for } x \in [\alpha_j, \alpha_{j+1}), j = 0, \dots, k\}$$

is a piecewise constant solution of the boundary value problem (1.1). Let us consider solutions of this boundary value problem with «close» to $\xi_*(x)$ initial conditions

$$\xi(t_0, x) = \{\rho_j + \xi_j(x), \text{ for } x \in [\alpha_j, \alpha_{j+1}), j = 0, \dots, k\}.$$

We call a solution $\xi_*(x)$ of the boundary value problem (1.1) α -Lyapunov stable if for each

$\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $\delta > 0$ such that from the condition $\max_x \sum_{j=1}^k |\xi_j(x)| < \delta$ follows the inequality $\max_x |\xi(t, x) - \xi_*(x)| < \varepsilon$ for all $t \geq t_0$.

If $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \max_x |\xi(t, x) - \xi_*(x)| = 0$, then the solution of $\xi_*(x)$ will be called *asymptotically α -stable*.

It follows from the above definitions that the question about α -stability of the solution on the interval $[0, 1]$ can be conditionally divided into the study of asymptotic stability separately on each of the intervals (α_j, α_{j+1}) . In addition, the Lyapunov theorem on stability on the first approximation is valid.

Similarly, we can introduce the notion α -instability. It is clear that from α -instability follows the instability of the solution.

Let us consider the stability of the piecewise constant solutions presented in lemmas 2.1, 2.2, 2.3. In the case of quadratic nonlinearity ($\beta = 1$) the following statement is satisfied.

Theorem 3.1. *For any $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, $\alpha \neq \frac{1}{2}$ the solution (2.2) of the boundary value problem (1.1)–(1.3) is unstable.*

PROOF

Let us represent the solution of the boundary value problem as

$$\xi(t, x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1-\alpha}{1-2\alpha} + \xi_1, & 0 \leq x < \alpha, \\ -\frac{\alpha}{1-2\alpha} + \xi_2, & \alpha \leq x < 1, \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

where $\xi_j = \xi_j(t, x)$, $j = 1, 2$ satisfy the condition

$$\int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x) dx + \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x) dx = 0. \quad (3.2)$$

Thus function (3.1) satisfies condition (1.3).

Substituting (3.1) into equation (1.1) and discarding the terms of a higher order of smallness, we obtain a system of differential equations

$$\frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{1-2\alpha} \xi_1 + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{1-2\alpha} \int_0^\alpha \xi_1 dx - \frac{2\alpha}{1-2\alpha} \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx,$$

$$\frac{\partial \xi_2}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{1-2\alpha} \xi_2 + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{1-2\alpha} \int_0^\alpha \xi_1 dx - \frac{2\alpha}{1-2\alpha} \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx.$$

Using condition (3.2) we obtain two independent equations

$$\frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{1-2\alpha} \xi_1 + \frac{2}{1-2\alpha} \int_0^\alpha \xi_1 dx, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \xi_2}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{1-2\alpha} \xi_2 - \frac{2}{1-2\alpha} \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx.$$

In system (3.3), we integrate the first equation by x from 0 to α , and the second

equation from α to 1. We obtain the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x) dx &= - \int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x) dx, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x) dx &= - \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x) dx, \end{aligned}$$

the solutions of which have the form

$$\int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x) dx = A_0 e^{-t}, \quad \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x) dx = B_0 e^{-t}.$$

Substituting the found integrals in (3.3), we obtain two linear inhomogeneous equations, the

solutions of which

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1(t, x) &= A(x)e^{-\frac{t}{1-2\alpha}} + \frac{A_0}{\alpha}e^{-t}, \\ \xi_2(t, x) &= B(x)e^{\frac{t}{1-2\alpha}} + \frac{B_0}{1-\alpha}e^{-t} \end{aligned} \quad \xi(t, x) = \begin{cases} \pm \frac{1-\alpha}{\sqrt{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2}} + \xi_1, & 0 \leq x < \alpha, \\ \mp \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2}} + \xi_2, & \alpha \leq x < 1, \end{cases} \quad (3.4)$$

do not tend to zero simultaneously at any $\alpha \neq \frac{1}{2}$. where $\xi_i = \xi_i(t, x)$, $i = 1, 2$ satisfy the condition

Let us now consider the case of cubic nonlinearity ($\beta = 0$).

Theorem 3.2. *Let $\frac{1}{3} < \alpha < \frac{2}{3}$. Then the solution of the form (2.3) of the boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3) is asymptotically α -stable.*

PROOF

Let us represent the solution of the boundary value problem as

$$\int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x)dx + \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x)dx = 0. \quad (3.5)$$

Let us substitute (3.4) into equation (1.1) and discard the terms of higher order of smallness. We obtain a system of ordinary differential equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial t} &= \frac{-2+3\alpha}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \xi_1 + \frac{3(1-\alpha)^2}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \int_0^\alpha \xi_1 dx + \frac{3\alpha^2}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx, \\ \frac{\partial \xi_2}{\partial t} &= \frac{1-3\alpha}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \xi_2 + \frac{3(1-\alpha)^2}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \int_0^\alpha \xi_1 dx + \frac{3\alpha^2}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx, \end{aligned}$$

then from the condition (3.5) we obtain

the second from α to 1. We obtain the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial t} &= \frac{-2+3\alpha}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \xi_1 + \frac{3-6\alpha}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \int_0^\alpha \xi_1 dx, \\ \frac{\partial \xi_2}{\partial t} &= \frac{1-3\alpha}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \xi_2 + \frac{6\alpha-3}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2} \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

As in the previous case, let us integrate the first equation of the system (3.6) by x from 0 to α , and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x)dx &= -2 \int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x)dx, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x)dx &= -2 \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx, \end{aligned}$$

whose solutions are equal to

$$\int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x)dx = A_0 e^{-2t}, \quad \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x)dx = B_0 e^{-2t}.$$

Substituting the found integrals into the system (3.6), we obtain two linear inhomogeneous

equations, the solutions of which

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_1(t, x) &= A(x)e^{\frac{-2+3\alpha}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2}t} + \frac{A_0}{\alpha}e^{-2t}, \\ \xi_2(t, x) &= B(x)e^{\frac{1-3\alpha}{1-3\alpha+3\alpha^2}t} + \frac{B_0}{1-\alpha}e^{-2t}\end{aligned}$$

tend to zero simultaneously at $\frac{1}{3} < \alpha < \frac{2}{3}$. At $\alpha = \frac{1}{3}$ and $\alpha = \frac{2}{3}$ it follows from the same formulas α -Lyapunov stability of the step solution. ■

In the case of arbitrary β similarly to the previous cases we construct a linearized system of ordinary differential equations. Let us represent the solution of the problem in the form

$$\xi(t, x) = \begin{cases} a(\alpha) + \xi_1, & 0 \leq x < \alpha, \\ b(\alpha) + \xi_2, & \alpha \leq x < 1, \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

where $a(\alpha)$, $b(\alpha)$ are determined by the formula (2.5), $\xi_j = \xi_j(t, x)$, ($j = 1, 2$), and ξ_j satisfy the condition

$$\int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x)dx + \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x)dx = 0. \quad (3.8)$$

Substituting (3.7) into (1.1) and discarding the terms of a higher order of smallness, we arrive at the system

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial t} &= a_1(\alpha)\xi_1 + b_1(\alpha) \int_0^\alpha \xi_1 dx + b_2(\alpha) \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx, \\ \frac{\partial \xi_2}{\partial t} &= a_2(\alpha)\xi_2 + b_1(\alpha) \int_0^\alpha \xi_1 dx + b_2(\alpha) \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx,\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}a_1(\alpha) &= 1 - 2\beta a(\alpha) - 3(1 - \beta)a^2(\alpha), \\ a_2(\alpha) &= 1 - 2\beta b(\alpha) - 3(1 - \beta)b^2(\alpha), \\ b_1(\alpha) &= 2\beta a(\alpha) + 3(1 - \beta)a^2(\alpha), \\ b_2(\alpha) &= 2\beta b(\alpha) + 3(1 - \beta)b^2(\alpha).\end{aligned}$$

Taking into account condition (3.8) we

obtain two equations independent of each other

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \xi_1}{\partial t} &= a_1(\alpha)\xi_1 + (b_1(\alpha) - b_2(\alpha)) \int_0^\alpha \xi_1 dx, \\ \frac{\partial \xi_2}{\partial t} &= a_2(\alpha)\xi_2 + (b_2(\alpha) - b_1(\alpha)) \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2 dx.\end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

Let us integrate the first equation of system (3.9) over x from 0 to α , and the second from α to 1. We obtain two equations

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x)dx &= d(\alpha) \int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x)dx, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x)dx &= d(\alpha) \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x)dx,\end{aligned}$$

whose solutions are equal to

$$\int_0^\alpha \xi_1(t, x)dx = A_0 e^{d(\alpha)t}, \quad \int_\alpha^1 \xi_2(t, x)dx = B_0 e^{d(\alpha)t}.$$

Substituting the found integrals in (3.9), we obtain two linear inhomogeneous equations, the solutions of which

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_1(t, x) &= A(x)e^{a_1(\alpha)t} + \frac{A_0}{\alpha}e^{d(\alpha)t}, \\ \xi_2(t, x) &= B(x)e^{a_2(\alpha)t} + \frac{B_0}{1-\alpha}e^{d(\alpha)t}\end{aligned}$$

tend to zero simultaneously at negative $a_1(\alpha)$, $a_2(\alpha)$, $d(\alpha)$.

Figure 1 shows numerically plotted graphs of functions $a_1(\alpha)$, $a_2(\alpha)$ and $d(\alpha)$ at different β . The analysis of these graphs suggests that are continuous on the interval $[0, 1]$ the functions $a_2(\alpha)$, $a_1(\alpha)$ change sign at the points $\alpha_0(\beta) \in (0, 1)$, $\alpha_1(\beta) \in (0, 1)$, respectively. For all considered $\beta \in (0, 1)$, these functions have a single sign-changing point and the inequality $\alpha_0(\beta) < \alpha_1(\beta)$ is satisfied. Moreover, both functions $a_2(\alpha)$ and $a_1(\alpha)$ are negative at $\alpha \in (\alpha_0, \alpha_1)$ and $d(\alpha) < 0$ for all $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. Thus, we can assume that for every $\beta \in (0, 1)$ there exists an interval

FIG. 1: (Color online) Graphs of $a_1(\alpha)$, $a_2(\alpha)$, and $d(\alpha)$ at different values of β .

$(\alpha_0, \alpha_1) \subset [0, 1]$ on which the functions $a_1(\alpha)$, $a_2(\alpha)$, and $d(\alpha)$ are negative at the same time. This means that for $\alpha \in (\alpha_0, \alpha_1)$, solutions of the form (3.7) of the boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3) are asymptotically α -stable.

4. Other attractors of the boundary value problem, numerical analysis

Since problem (1.1)-(1.3) is dissipative in the case $\beta \neq 1$, it makes sense to study the dynamics of solutions of the boundary value problem outside the interval α -stability of piecewise constant solutions having one discontinuity point.

It can be proved that with only cubic nonlinearity the boundary value problem has α -stable piecewise constant solutions with values 1 and -1 . Let us show that this is indeed true.

Let the piecewise constant function $\xi(t, x)$ have $n + 1$ a discontinuity point α_j , $j = 0, \dots, n$ and on the intervals $[\alpha_{j-1}, \alpha_j]$ equal to $(-1)^{j-1}$. Moreover, $\alpha_0 = 0$, $\alpha_n = 1$. Then from the zero mean condition (1.3) we obtain the equation on the values $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{n-1}$

$$2\alpha_1 - 2\alpha_2 + 2\alpha_3 + \dots + 2(-1)^n \alpha_n + (-1)^{n+1} = 0. \quad (4.1)$$

Substituting $\xi(t, x)$ into equation (1.1), we see that $M(\xi^3)$ is also zero. Then on the intervals $[\alpha_{j-1}, \alpha_j]$ equation (1.1) takes the form

$$0 = (-1)^{j-1} - (-1)^{3(j-1)},$$

which is obviously a true equality. Consequently, if condition (4.1) in the case of cubic nonlinearity is satisfied, the boundary value problem (1.1)-(1.3) really has solutions of the considered form.

FIG. 2: The α -stable solutions of the form (2.3) in the case $\beta = 0$.

FIG. 3: The α -unstable solutions of the form (2.4).

Let us consider the α -stability of these solutions. Let

$$\xi(t, x) = (-1)^{j-1} + \xi_j(t, x), \text{ for } x \in [\alpha_{j-1}, \alpha_j],$$

then

$$M(\xi) = \sum_{j=1}^n \int_{\alpha_{j-1}}^{\alpha_j} \xi_j(t, x) dx = 0.$$

Let us substitute $\xi(t, x)$ into equation (1.1) and discard the terms of higher order of smallness.

Note that in this case

$$\begin{aligned} M(\xi^3) &= \sum_{j=1}^n \int_{\alpha_{j-1}}^{\alpha_j} ((-1)^{j-1} + \xi_j(t, x))^3 dx \\ &= 3 \sum_{j=1}^n \int_{\alpha_{j-1}}^{\alpha_j} \xi_j(t, x) dx = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we obtain a system of linear differential equations

$$\frac{\partial \xi_j}{\partial t} = -2\xi_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, n-1,$$

FIG. 4. The initial conditions of the boundary value problem as a function (3.4) with a small perturbation added.

FIG. 5. The initial conditions of the boundary value problem as a function (3.4) with a high-frequency perturbation added.

solutions of which tend to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, the piecewise constant solutions considered α -stable.

Nevertheless, the question about the existence of other piecewise constant solutions of the boundary value problem at different values β and the question α -stability of these solutions remains open.

The analytical study in this case presents a certain difficulty, so it is appropriate to investigate the behavior of solutions to the boundary value problem by numerical methods.

We will search for the solution of the

boundary value problem in the form of a partial sum of the Fourier series

$$\xi(t, x) = \sum_{k=-N}^N \xi_k(t) \exp(2\pi kix). \quad (4.2)$$

Such representation obviously satisfies the boundary condition (1.2). Since the zero mean condition (1.3) implies that the Fourier series coefficient at the zero harmonic is zero, we consider that (4.2) holds in $\xi_0(t) \equiv 0$. Also $\xi_{-k}(t) = \bar{\xi}_k(t)$.

Substituting (4.2) into (1.1) and singling out the coefficients at the same harmonics, we obtain

the system of $2N$ ordinary differential equations

$$\dot{\xi}_k = \xi_k - \beta \left(\xi_{k/2}^2 + 2 \sum_{i+j=k} \xi_i \xi_j \right) - (1 - \beta) \left(\xi_{k/3}^3 + 3 \sum_{2i+j=k} \xi_i^2 \xi_j + 6 \sum_{i+j+l=k} \xi_i \xi_j \xi_l \right), \quad (4.3)$$

$$k = -N, \dots, N, k \neq 0.$$

The initial condition $\xi(0, x)$ is also presented as a partial sum of the Fourier series

$$\xi(0, x) = \sum_{k=-N}^N c_k \exp(2\pi k i x), \quad c_0 = 0.$$

Then the system (4.3) is considered with initial conditions

$$\xi_k(0) = c_k, \quad k = -N, \dots, N, \quad k \neq 0. \quad (4.4)$$

Thus, the numerical solution of the boundary value problem (1.1)–(1.3) is defined by formula (4.2), where $\xi_k(t)$ is the solution of system (4.3).

Let us construct a solution of problem (1.1)–(1.3) with initial condition $\xi(0, x) = \xi_0(x) + g(x)$, where $\xi_0(x)$ is a solution of the form (2.4), and $g(x)$ is a small perturbation satisfying the boundary conditions (1.2), (1.3).

Figure 2 below shows an example of α -stable solutions of the form (2.3) in the case $\beta = 0$.

Let us now take such a value α at which a solution of the form (2.4) is unstable. Then as $t \rightarrow \infty$ the solutions tend to piecewise constant functions having several discontinuities. Figure 3 shows an example of such a solution. The left side shows the initial condition of the boundary value problem as a graph of the function (3.4) with a small perturbation added. The figure on the right shows the same solution at $t = 15$. It represents a piecewise constant function with several discontinuity points. Note that a further increase in the values of the variable t does not change the structure of the solution, its graph does not differ from the graph in the right part of Figure 3.

Moreover, if at a fixed $\xi_0(x)$ one takes as a perturbation $g(x)$ a function of the form $A \sin(kx)$, there is a dependence of the number of breaking points α -stable piecewise permanent solution on the parameter k . Namely, the more k , the more number of breaking points has piecewise constant solution obtained when calculating the solution of the system (4.3). Figure 4 shows the initial condition of the boundary value problem as a function (3.4) with a small perturbation added. With increasing values of the variable t , the solution takes the form of a piecewise constant function with several discontinuity points. Figure 5 shows a graph of a similar initial condition to which a perturbation with a larger frequency of oscillation is added. Increasing the value of the variable t in this case leads the solution to a piecewise constant function with a larger number of breakpoints.

5. Conclusion

The dynamics of solutions of the boundary value problem (1.1)–(1.3) at different values of the parameter β was investigated. It was proved that for each β the problem has one or two one-parameter families of piecewise constant solutions depending on the parameter α . The α -stability of these solutions is investigated. It is shown that at $\beta \neq 1$ there exists an interval of variation of parameter α , at which these solutions are asymptotically α -stable. It is proved that in the case $\beta = 1$ all such solutions are unstable.

During the numerical experiment, an algorithm based on the method of expansions in Fourier series was used. With its help, it was

expedient to calculate solutions of the boundary value problem that satisfy the condition of zero mean. The behavior of solutions of the boundary value problem for $\beta \neq 1$ outside the domain of definition of an α -stable one-parameter family of piecewise constant solutions is studied numerically. The presence of α -stable piecewise constant solutions with more than one discontinuity point is shown. Thus, it is shown that there is a good closeness between the theoretical results and the numerical experiment.

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